

The SAAL process and the interpretation of domesticity: the singularity and miscegenation of its housing models

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1. Introduction:

After a period when the Modernists and Functionalists were mainly focused on the theory of housing, the SAAL process appears at a moment when architecture was defined by an overturn that put the emphasis on the need to rethink the city, a process in which social inclusion played a very important role. The changing trajectory was already noticeable during the construction of Le Corbusier's Unités d'Habitation (1952/1967), at the same time when the CIAM began to dissolve: the 1950's were already defined by the Nordic Empiricism, which turned to the garden-city as an urban model again (Montaner, 2001), but also by the emergence of TEAM X, which considered Modernism decontextualized, Functionalism excessively mechanized and the International Style as a destroyer of individual identity (Frampton & Riambau i Sauri, 1996).

The New Brutalism, associated with the Smithsons, was still considering megastructures as urban reference points (Frampton & Riambau i Sauri, 1996): their notions of "cluster" and "stem" (Smithson & Smithson, 1967) introduced the sequence "block, village, city", in which the "house" was

no longer the origin of the city. In practice, their experience was not much different from the Modern one, and their reinterpretation of the traditional street in the "sky" (galleries where "people can stop and talk, and where entrance doors, for their sheltered location, create spaces for 'breaks'" (French, 2008, p. 150)) did not replace the recreational nature of the street and deprived the dwellers of their privacy (Portas, 2005b).

On the opposite pole we find the Italian Neorealism, with a completely different formal and ideological origin (associated with the New Empiricism, followed by the Italians with interest (Portas, 2004) (Montaner, 2001)): in Italy the destruction caused by World War II had been reduced (Benevolo, 2006), annulling the "urgency" that guided the Modern mentality. However, the Fascists had castrated the underprivileged population, so the INA-Casa Program was created to overcome the lack of houses.

Together with the need to contradict the historicist aesthetics (a Fascist legacy) there was a closer relationship with the Individual, which had been denied by Modernism and Fascism in favour of the collectivity. The

1. Mexilhoeira, Algarve.

2. Castelo, Ferreira do Alentejo.

Common Man (Perin, Pena, & Rodrigues, 2009) became the target of an art whose aim was to portray the real living conditions of the people, using the “Neorrealist” movies as its main form of communication (Reichlin, Shugaar, & Joseph, 2001).

This closer relationship with the Individual was also physical, leading the architects to question people about their physical and psychological needs. Using the amounts withheld from the workers’ wages (controlled by a central public organization (Muratori, 1952)), the INA-CASA (Istituto Nazionale delle Assicurazioni) built affordable housing estates promoting a close cooperation between architects and dwellers, and surveying the people’s housing aspirations in order to materialize them in its proposals (Portas, 2004). So, we can see that the desired kitchen owed nothing to the Frankfurtkuche (Neves, 2005), remaining at the centre of family life with an equally significant area. Or that the bedrooms, more than a technical sleeping area, needed to be private spaces for multiple activities, while the living room worked as a reception space.

2. Sequels on Portuguese grounds

Neorealism was a reference for SAAL (also in Olivais, a southern attempt to create streets and blocks “whose meaning was diminished by the passing of time” (Portas, 2005c, p. 496)). As a process, the similarities end here, because the GTH (Gabinete Técnico de Habitação) gave total creative freedom to the architects involved, as long as they did not exceed the agreed budget (Nunes, 2007, p. 66). In Olivais, the inquiries were made after the houses had been built in order to assess the satisfaction of the dwellers (Bandeirinha, 2007), who were pleased because they had moved in from shacks (Nunes, 2007). But Bandeirinha (2007) mentions that the population felt out of context in what regarded the urban space and the dwellings’ layout, making changes that modified their use and formality (closed kitchens, bedrooms turned into living rooms); these issues were highlighted by Portas in “A habitação social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura” [Social housing: proposal for a methodology of its architecture] (2004), published in 1969 and based on inquiries, since he also wanted to get closer to the Real Man and his needs, as he had already mentioned in “Arquitetura Integrada?” [Integrated Architecture?], published in 1963 (Portas, 2005a).

3. Cortegaça, Aveiro.

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4. Batateiro, Seixal.

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3. House versus City

The “rules” defined by Portas to organize the domestic space in social housing reflect the changes made by the dwellers to the first estates built in Olivais, mentioning the Nordic and Italian proposals as his ideological grounds (despite the criticism made to the Italian urban design). Given its almost scientific accuracy, Portas’ guide had everything to become a reference for the SAAL process in terms of domesticity, since it was based on real experiences and on inquiries to the interested parties: the SAAL process was supported by the “brigades” that worked closely with the people in order to answer the real needs when it came to designing “their” homes. In other words, it was the Individual Identity associated with the Urban Context “versus” the Universal Man associated with the Domestic Space.

The latter seems to have been “abandoned” by its contemporary theory, so in the SAAL process it seems to have been a subject that was rarely considered. However, it is noticeable that the reflection on the domestic space was not neglected: identifying the users in order to reflect them had to have an expression in the houses’ internal organization. We can understand

this absence of theory, not only due to the fact that the “House” had been replaced by the “City”, but also because there were already various experimented housing layout models. The abolition of dogmas allowed the emergence of a variety of solutions that could be reinterpreted according to specific circumstances. In short, there was no longer the need for “controversy”.

To each dogma we can always associate the architect’s personal interpretation and the introduction of regionalisms (Correia, 2008) but, in order to support the study and analysis we want to carry out, there is the need to resort to them in order to summarize the reasoning on dwelling within the SAAL process in an understandable way.

The Functionalist type, based on the separation of living spaces according to their use, consisted of a tripartite house divided into areas intended to be common, private, or simply utilitarian (where the kitchen was included). If we place the family (Stigar, 2008) at the core of this type, we see that it defines the spatial organization: the level of privacy between its members, measured through the domestic actions performed by each of them, determined that leisure took place in common spaces and intimacy behind doors. In short,

5. Casal das Figueiras, Setúbal.

6. Catujal, Loures.

the house was designed considering only its permanent occupants.

Excessively mechanized, this type intended to be the coherent alternative to the bourgeois model, used by Karl Ehn in Karl Marx Hof, but it sacrificed facilities like the bathroom (Teige, 2002). The minimum areas did not change its basic nature: privacy measured between the house's dwellers and the external elements. In its origin, Alberti's palatial model (Mesquita, 1992) was a series of spaces arranged along an enfilade to which the visitors were allowed access according to their closeness: a formal entrance, a room for representative purposes, one for recreational purposes and, finally, the space where private life of the family as a whole unfolded.

The development of a closer relationship with people and their aspirations, which we have already mentioned, created a third way characterized by its multiplicity and adequacy to the dwellers, defined not only as physiological and social entities, but also as geographic and cultural beings. Empiricism and Neorealism gave shape to this approach and we can consider that the SAAL process took these two movements as its references.

4. The SAAL process and the domestic space

This article is, therefore, an instrument of analysis of the internal layout of some of the proposals made within the scope of the SAAL process. The methodology we used was retrieved from a previous study (Jorge, 2012), in which the affordable housing unit was analyzed under the “pseudonym” Minimum Cell: the “living space with the minimum volume needed by the occupants to perform all their functional and social movements” (Jorge, 2012, p. 33), a definition that is nevertheless generic because, throughout the analytical process, different models revealed different understandings and concepts.

5. Methodology:

The choice of the models was made in an empirical, but never anarchical, way. From the collection made by José António Bandeirinha (2007), we chose the models that, due to the spacial solutions that were used, raised, either certainties, or doubts. These were subject to a study process similar to the one used in the aforementioned Thesis, which involved redesigning the plans, “furnishing” them (a method used to find a comparative scale, but also as a way to discover different uses) and defining paths.

6. On the studied models:

It is in the common areas of the housing unit that we can most clearly find different interpretations of the spaces that shape it. The intended exchange of information between architects and users did not result in models with a similar physical and functional separation, since this resulted from different interpretations of family relationships (or, more comprehensively, of the Domestic Group relationships (Afonso, 2000)), or of the relationships between these and the external elements.

In Mexilhoeira, Algarve, there is a clear separation between the spaces used by the dwellers and what we can define as a reception space for an occasional and formal use: the existence of a double entrance (one for the kitchen, and the other to the aforementioned space) indicates, not a hierarchy, but a differentiation of the use ascribed to each space. The kitchen is clearly the “centre” of the house, because its size allows having a table and using the space on a regular basis, but also because the bedrooms converge towards it. There is “a privacy” that belongs to the domestic group but not to the visitors, who have a private access to a separate space. In Castelo, Ferreira do Alentejo, we

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find a similar solution, despite the different shape of the house: the double façade allows accessing the kitchen “through the back-door” (using a service “patio”). The circulation between all the spaces that compose the house is carefully controlled by the corridor; again, the kitchen seems to be the heart of the house (Lynch, 2008), due to its size and to the existence of a fireplace (also used for cooking) that makes the space comfortable during the winter: we can see which of the spaces was intended to have a more intensive use, however, we can also assume that the living room was the space intended to have better furniture. The need to have a filtered entrance may be associated with the bourgeois model (and all the similarities with it end here), but the popular housing models also had the need to be provided with some kind of “representativeness”, limited to the “china cupboard” of the rural kitchens, where the best crockery was displayed (Jorge, 2006).

Therefore, part of the process of turning the entire house into a “usable” space implied rethinking the relationship between access and transition spaces, i.e., exchanging the privacy relationships between domestic and public (Bourgeois) and private and common (Modern). In Cortegaça, Aveiro, this last model is used in an (almost) uncritical way: although the unit has two entrances, the main one – connected to the street – opens directly into the living room (the minimum kitchen is protected by a wall); this, together with the fact that the living room is more broadly open to the plot’s interior reveals a will to turn this into a space of permanence. The functional separation from the rest of the house is made easier by the existence of two floors (bedrooms on the top floor), but the stairs open directly to the living room (highlighting it as a “distributive” space, a solution that goes against Nuno Portas’ recommendations (Portas, 2004) (Portas, 2005b), precisely due to its implications for the privacy of the domestic group). Finally, we should note the great terrace located on the upper floor, which is likely to be partially occupied by a future extension.

However, we should interpret this approach according to its influence in a contained house: allowing the “usable” area to be extended as

much as possible. Due to the influence of the dwellers and to the awareness that the family's privacy is valued in southern Europe, there were attempts to achieve compromise solutions in which the living room, despite not being closed, offers some sort of protection from the entrance: in Batateiro, Seixal, the corridor leads directly to the kitchen and to the stairs to the upper floor, but it is contained by a wall that goes halfway up across the living room. This solution does not invalidate the dining area as the living room's focal point, because it is large and separated from the kitchen (which is minimal – and a Functionalist legacy?). We can also interpret this autonomous dining space as a legacy of the Italian Neorealism: the inquiries to the population revealed the desire for a room apart from the kitchen that could be used for meals, but also to carry out small domestic tasks. It was known as “lavoro” (Portas, 1969) and mentioned by José António Bandeirinha (2007) as used by Alexandre Alves Costa in his Grupo de Moradias Populares de Contumil [Contumil Social Houses Group] (1969/76), working as a “space for an undifferentiated use” (2007, p. 104).

We can find similar solutions in Catujal, Loures, and Casal de Figueiras, Setúbal: an access controlled by a small “pillar” that does not interfere with the perception of the living room. In the first example, since there are no doors to separate the kitchen/dining area/living area, the pantry was designed in order to conceal the kitchen from the visitors without interrupting the circulation's fluidity: the dining area becomes a space that is accessible from the kitchen, which made it unnecessary to provide the kitchen with a larger area. Casal das Figueiras also stands out for a similarly fluid circulation and, depending on the number of bedrooms, some types allow the dwellers to circulate around the stairs, providing them with a private access from the kitchen to the living room.

What makes these two models stand out is the existence, on the upper floor, of a space with an undefined use connected to the corridor; these spaces are placed next to the façade and, therefore, very well lit. In Casal das Figueiras this space has a balcony. Since it “belongs” to the Domestic Group, it presupposes an awareness that the domestic

uses cannot be completely defined in an indisputable way; so, this space may have a completely private, recreational or work-related use.

But while in Catujal this space can easily be turned into a bedroom, in Casal Das Figueiras that is less likely, because closing it would result in a very reduced, and even uninhabitable area. In Lapa, Porto, we may consider that the widening of the circulation space on the second floor fits into this category, but the fact that it does not have natural light reduces its quality in comparison with ones mentioned above.

Another particularity found in Lapa, but also in Santo António, Camarate, and Cortegaça, is the “inversion” of the living room's location, which is placed on the back of the house (placing a bedroom on the façade...), thus favouring its seclusion and daily use.

One of the most curious proposals is the one designed for Relvinha, Coimbra: the Types are divided according to their number of bedrooms (T2, T3 and T4), but attached to the entrance there is an enclosed space, with a very small area, whose purpose is undefined. We could consider it as a multifunctional space, like the previous examples, but its size, the fact that it is enclosed and, especially, its location, seem to suggest that this space might be a small “parlour”. It is open towards an entrance hall (a unique feature among the selected examples) that controls the access to the following spaces: living room, dining room, kitchen, access to the upper floor, which are “hidden” and likely to be used on a daily basis.

7. A few concluding remarks

The absence of a specific program for the houses, as well as the existence of very different budgets, led the SAAL to produce different solutions; while in Mexilhoeira the self-construction process allowed building a T3 house with 150m², in Cortegaça it was only possible to reach an area of 71m² for the same type of house. There is a Modern legacy that was repeatedly used in what regards the conquest of individual privacy: the existence of private bedrooms that contrast with the

common areas, which vary according to the references used in the control of private/common/outdoor areas. We can mention solutions like large common spaces that are open towards the (more or less protected) entrance, and even the reinterpretation of the multifunctional dining room (lavoro?) based on a fluid circulation.

More important, perhaps, is the proposal of a space with an undefined use that allows adjusting the house to unforeseen uses, a central issue in contemporary housing but that, in this case, was applied in models designed in 1970's with very limited areas and costs.

Bibliography

- Afonso, A. I. (2000). Grupo Doméstico e Mudança Social: abordagens quantitativas e qualitativas. *Etnográfica IV*, 153–182.
- Bandeirinha, J. A. (2007). *O processo SAAL e a arquitetura no 25 de abril de 1974*. Coimbra: Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra.
- Benevolo, L. (2006). *História da arquitetura moderna*. Perspectiva.
- Correia, G. (2008). *Ruy d'Athouguia: a modernidade em aberto*. Casal de Cambra, Portugal: Caleidoscópio.
- Frampton, K., & Riambau i Sauri, E. (1996). *Historia crítica de la arquitectura moderna*. Barcelona: Gustavo Gili.
- French, H. (2008). Key urban housing of the twentieth century. London: Laurence King.
- Fuertes, P., & Monteys, X. (2002). *Casa Collage*. Barcelona: Gustavo Gili.
- Jorge, P. (2006). *A casa rural no concelho de Alcobaça em 1961: da teorização erudita à prática popular*. Master Thesis, Department of Architecture, University of Coimbra.
- Jorge, P. (2012). *A célula mínima na experiência da habitação de custos controlados*. Master Thesis, Faculty of Architecture, University of Porto.
- Lynch, K. (2008). Aldo Rossi Knew all about the symbolic power of a kitchen table. *The Architects' Journal 2*.
- Mesquita, M. D. (1992). *História e Arquitectura, uma proposta de investigação – o palácio dos Marqueses de Fronteira como situação exemplar da Arquitectura Residencial Erudita em Portugal*. Master Thesis, Faculty of Architecture, University of Lisbon.
- Montaner, J. M. (2001). *Depois do movimento moderno: arquitetura da segunda metade do século XX*. Barcelona: Gustavo Gili.
- Muratori, S. (1952). La Gestioni INA-Casa e l'edilizia popolare in Italia. *Rassegna Critica D'architettura 41*, 3–88.
- Neves, G. (2005). *Ideologia e Cultura na República de Veimar – A arquitetura e o planeamento urbano de Ernst May*. University of Coimbra.
- Nunes, J. (2007). *Lisboa, arquitetura e urbanismo à escala humana: planeamento urbano e arquitetura de habitação em Olivais Sul, Lisboa 1959-1969*. Lisbon: Câmara Municipal de Lisboa.

Perin, A., Pena, J., & Rodrigues, G. (2009). *O Neo-realismo italiano e suas influências*. Retrieved from <http://pt.scribd.com/doc/17704198/O-Neo-realismo-italiano-e-suas-influencias>

Portas, N. (1969). *Funções e Exigências de Áreas da Habitação* (Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil.). Lisbon: Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil.

Portas, N. (2004). *A habitação social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura*. Porto: Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto.

Portas, N. (2005a). *Arquitectura Integrada?* In *História e Crítica, Ensino e Profissão* (Vol. 23). Porto: Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto.

Portas, N. (2005b). *Considerações sobre o organismo distributivo das habitações*. In *Arquitectura(s): teoria e desenho, investigação e projecto* (Vols. 1-3, Vol. 3). Porto: Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto.

Portas, N. (2005c). *Olivais: o retrato de um bairro*. In *Arquitectura(s): teoria e desenho, investigação e projecto* (Vol. 23, p. 496). Porto: Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto.

Reichlin, B., Shugaar, A., & Joseph, B. W. (2001). *Figures of Neorealism in Italian Architecture (Part 1)*. *Grey Room 5*, 79–101. doi:10.2307/1262574

Smithson, A. M., & Smithson, P. (1967). *Urban structuring: studies of Alison & Peter Smithson*. London; New York: Studio Vista; Reinhold.

Stigar, R. (2008, November 9). *As novas concepções de família*. Retrieved from <http://www.webartigos.com/artigos/as-novas-concepcoes-de-familia/9248/>

Swenarton, M. (2008). *Building the New Jerusalem: Architecture, Housing and Politics 1900-1930* (1 edition.). Bracknell England: IHS BRE Press.

Teige, K. (2002). *The minimum dwelling = L'habitation minimum = Die Kleinstwohnung: the housing crisis, housing reform*. Cambridge, Mass. : Chicago, Ill: MIT Press ; Graham Foundation for Advanced Studies in the Fine Arts.